

STUDIES ON GUM JEOL (*LANNEA GRANDIS*, SUPER).
PART IV. ELECTRODIALYSIS*

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Gum jeol and gum arabic have been electro dialysed in the presence and absence of acids and have been found to be hydrolysed in all cases to the jeolic and arabic acid stage (mild hydrolysis). These acids have been found to behave almost similarly as regards freezing point depression, potentiometric titration with NaOH, total acidity and equivalent weight.

In previous communication of this series (Parts II and III, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 63, 113) the gum has been hydrolysed by H_2SO_4 to yield different products which are mainly reducing sugars (viz., *l*-arabinose and *d*-galactose) and an acid. Hydrolysis takes place in several stages depending on the strength of the acid used. With H_2SO_4 having concentration *ca* 0.5*N* (mild hydrolysis) a quantity of the above sugars and an acid (jeolic acid), forming colloidal solution in water, are obtained. With higher concentrations of H_2SO_4 (*ca*. 1*N*) the acid so obtained breaks down to yield a further quantity of sugars and another acid (aldobionic acid) which appears to form a true solution in water (as opposed to colloidal solution), and with still higher concentration of H_2SO_4 (*ca* 1.5*N*) this latter acid again breaks down to a hexose (*d*-galactose) and a hexuronic acid (galacturonic acid).

Mild hydrolysis with H_2SO_4 thus yields the jeolic acid, which appears to be sufficiently stable. In the present investigation results of electro dialysis of the gum solution have been recorded and compared with those of a solution of arabic acid. Hydrolysis, if any, in the dialysing chamber has been the principal point of interest.

EXPERIMENTAL

Electrodialysis in presence of Acids.—Crude gum (80 g.) was dissolved in a minimum amount of water and freed from suspended impurities by filtration. The gum was precipitated out by 50% alcohol and the process repeated thrice to obtain the purified sample which was thoroughly washed with alcohol and dried at room temperature. This air-dried sample (20 g. approx.) was dissolved in a little of conductivity water (sp. conduc. = 1.5×10^{-8} mho). Hydrochloric acid in sufficient quantity was added to make the solution 0.1*N* and the mixture was then electro dialysed in a three-compartment electro dialyser (Pauli pattern) for about 70 hours with a current strength of 0.4 to 0.5 amp. at 220 volts by using parchment membranes against distilled water. Collodion membranes were also tried but were found to behave almost like the parchment membrane, and hence the latter was preferred for low cost and easy availability. The gum

* A part of this work was carried out in the Physical Chemistry Laboratories of the University College of Science, Calcutta. In the previous parts the botanical name appeared as *Odina Wodier*, Roxb., an older name.

solution was taken in the middle compartment and water in the outer ones was allowed to flow continuously at a slow rate.

During electro dialysis water in the anode compartment was found to be acidic to bromothymol blue, while that in the cathodic chamber was alkaline. At the end of the period of 70 hours, the liquids in both the chambers reached practically neutral p_a (7). The liquid in the anode chamber as well as the solution in the middle compartment were tested by $AgNO_3$, to be free from chlorine.

The waters running out from the anode and cathode chambers were separately collected, concentrated by evaporation *in vacuo*, each made up to a definite volume (250 c.c.), and tested for reducing sugars by Fehling's solution. Sugars were found to be present in both the liquids. A portion of the solution from the cathode chamber was also examined qualitatively and found to contain Ca, Mg and K. A quantitative estimation of Ca, Mg, K and the reducing sugars (as glucose) was carried out by the usual methods and expressed as percentage of the air-dried, purified specimen as presented in Table I. The solution in the middle compartment was observed to be colloidal in nature and was highly acidic. Two samples of gum jeol were treated in a similar manner (Samples 1 and 3 of Part I, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 59). The solutions from the middle compartment are designated as sol A and sol B respectively.

An exactly similar procedure for electro dialysis was followed in the case of a gum arabic solution, previously purified by thrice precipitation with alcohol (50%), and similarly treated with HCl (0.1N). In this case it was observed that Ca, Mg and K were coming out into the cathodic chamber and Cl into the anode compartment but there was no indication for the liberation of reducing sugars into any of the outer compartments as in the case of gum jeol. Electro dialysis was continued till the central and the anode compartments were free from chlorine (Sol D). Solutions from the two outer compartments were separately collected, concentrated by evaporation at reduced pressure and each made up to a definite volume (250 c.c.). Quantitative estimations of sugar, Ca, Mg and K were carried out as before and presented in Table I.

Electro dialysis in absence of Acids.—About 100 g. of gum jeol (sample 1 of Part I) were purified by thrice precipitation with alcohol (50%) and the purified sample dried. This purified gum (20 g.) was dissolved in water and electro dialysed directly without addition of acid.

The current passing through the solution was observed in the beginning to be 0.15 amp. but in 8 hours' time it came down to 0.05 amp. only. By this time some of the gum settled down in the middle chamber which on stirring formed a uniform mixture and the current again increased to 0.1 amp. which slowly decreased with the progress of electro dialysis.

Six hours after electro dialysis was started and onwards, small quantities of liquids from the anode and cathode chambers were repeatedly tested for reducing sugars, Ca, Mg and K. Sugars were observed to come out into both the outer chambers while Ca, Mg and K were detected in the cathode chamber only. After about 65 hours the cations and sugars were found to be absent in each of the anode and cathode chambers. The

solution in the middle chamber was tested for the cations and a complete absence of these was an indication to stop further electro dialysis. A quantitative estimation of the sugars and the cations was carried out in an exactly similar manner as previously described, the results of which appear in Table I. The solution in the middle compartment has been termed Sol C.

Similar experimentation was resorted to in the case of gum arabic (purified) and the results are presented along with others in Table I (sol E).

TABLE I

Gum samples.	Conc. of added acid.	Anode compt. sugars*	Cathode compartment.			Total sugars.		Complex acid.	
			Ca.	Mg.	K.	Electro-dialysis.	Hydrolysis.		
Gum jeol.									
Sample 1	0.1 N	14.2%	0.8%	0.45%	0.10%	15.0%	29.2%	31%	68.7%
„	0	15.1	0.82	0.41	0.11	15.3	30.4	—	69.0
Sample 3	0.1	15.6	0.71	0.50	0.07	14.8	30.4	29.5	71.2
Gum Arabic.									
1	0.1	0.5	0.80	0.05	0.12	0.1	0.6	—	98.7
2	0	0.2	0.82	0.03	0.15	0.3	0.5	—	98.2

* Sugars have been estimated by titration with Fehling's solution and expressed as percentage of glucose.

It will be evident from the table that the amounts of sugars coming out in the two outer compartments are almost equal and the total amount from the two compartments roughly equals that obtained by mild hydrolysis of the gum with acid (vide Part II, *loc. cit.*) in the case of gum jeol, whether acid be used during electro dialysis or not. The total amount of the bases expressed as oxide is roughly equal to the percentage of ash obtained by incineration of the purified gum (about 3%). Ca appears to be the largest in amount, while Mg comes intermediate in gum jeol, and least in gum arabic. The percentage of sugars liberated during electro dialysis of gum arabic is very small.

The acid solutions from the central compartments were then made up to 1000 c.c. in each case. Aliquot portions of these were then precipitated by alcohol, and the precipitate after washing with alcohol, and finally with alcohol-ether mixture was dried in air. The amounts of the acid recovered in this way, expressed as percentage of the purified gum, have been presented in the last column of Table I. Combustion experiments of these acid samples present the following figures (Table II).

Evidently from Table II the acids, obtained from gum jeol by electro dialysis with or without acid and also by the mild hydrolysis of the gum, as well as those obtained from gum arabic by similar methods have almost the same percentage composition. Whether the acids are of the same order of complexity (i. e., molecular weight) was tested by determination of the freezing point of a 10% solution of these which showed an approxi-

mate lowering of 0.2° . The molecular weights in aqueous solution of all these acids therefore appear to be equal.

TABLE II

Details of the sample.	Carbon.	Hydrogen.	Oxygen.
Gum jeol.			
1. Acid from sample 1 of gum jeol, electro dialysed with acid	39.5%	6.4%	54.0%
2. Acid from the same sample, electro dialysed without acid	39.1	7.0	53.2
3. Acid from another sample, electro dialysed with acid	39.8	6.5	53.2
4. Jeolic acid obtained from mild hydrolysis of the gum	39.3	6.1	54.2
Gum Arabic.			
1. Acid from the sample electro dialysed with acid	40.1	6.0	54.3
2. Acid from the same, electro dialysed without acid	40.5	6.2	53.9
3. Arabic acid obtained by hydrolysis of the gum	40.1	6.7	53.5

Hence, the only conclusion from these data appears to be that the acids obtained by the mild hydrolysis of the gum and by electro dialysis are probably the same for each gum. The acids for the two different gums have also the same composition and probably the same molecular weight.

Further examination was carried out by potentiometric titration (with NaOH) of 1% solutions of all these acids, the results of which have been shown in Table III. The procedure adopted for carrying out these titrations will be presented in details in a subsequent communication.

TABLE III

Conc. of solution = 1%. Temp. = $35^\circ \pm 0.1$.

Details of the acid.	p^H at inflexion.	Total acidity per 100 g. of acid.	Eq. wt.
Gum jeol.			
Sol A (by electro dialysis with acid)	7.1	$91 \times 10^{-3}N$	1099
Sol B (Do from another gum)	7.2	88	1137
Sol C (Do, without acid in the same gum specimen as sol A)	7.2	89	1124
Sol A* (by hydrolysis with H_2SO_4)	7.0	87	1150
Gum Arabic.			
Sol D (by electro dialysis with acid)	7.0	89	1124
Sol E (Do, without acid)	7.15	87	1150
Sol D* (by hydrolysis with H_2SO_4)	7.1	89	1124

Sol A and sol D* have been obtained from the same gum specimens as the sols A and D respectively by hydrolysis of the gums with H_2SO_4 (conc. $\approx 0.5N$).

It has been observed that the curves for all the acids are similar and they all resemble the curve for strong monobasic acids (like HCl) so far as their shape and the p_n of inflexion are concerned.

FIG. 1

Potentiometric titration curve for the complex jeolic acid.

Only one curve for titration of jeolic acid by NaOH has been shown in Fig. 1 as typical of the class. There is hardly any difference by the help of which they can be distinguished from one another. The acids obtained from gum jeol by the different procedures are exactly alike and those from gum arabic are also alike amongst themselves. Acids from the two gums are again similar to one another. Thus, from potentiometric titration it is not possible to distinguish these acids from one another. The equivalent weights calculated from the total acidity are almost equal, being about 1100 (approx.). This aspect will from the subject matter of a

future communication.

CONCLUSIONS

Both gum jeol and gum arabic on electro dialysis with or without acid yield an acid which has been obtained in the pure state.

The acid so obtained for each gum (by electro dialysis with and without acid) simulate one another in points of freezing point depression, potentiometric titration curves, total acidity and equivalent weight.

These acids also simulate the jeolic acid and arabic acid obtained by mild hydrolysis of the respective gums by H_2SO_4 (conc. $\approx 0.5N$).

From this observation it may therefore be concluded that the gum jeol is hydrolysed by electro dialysis even without acid and forms the same jeolic acid as obtained by its mild hydrolysis with H_2SO_4 . The jeolic acid thus appears to be a fairly stable substance (cf. Part III, this *Journal* 1948, 25, 113) and forms an intermediate step in the hydrolysis of the gum. The jeolic acid and the corresponding acid from gum arabic (arabic acid) are also very much alike so far as some of their physical properties, as have been studied herein, are concerned.

Electrodialysis of the two gums show that gum jeol is a much more complex substance than gum arabic. While gum arabic appears to be a Ca, Mg or K salt of the arabic acid, the other gum is also a mixture of the same salts of the jeolic acid but contains in addition some additional sugar molecules which remain more or less loosely bound as evident from the fact that some sugars have been found to be liberated on electro dialysis of the gum even in absence of acids. Electro dialysis of gum arabic without acid yields negligibly small quantities of sugars. Hence we conclude that gum jeol is a more complex body, being salt of jeolic acid to which some sugar molecules are further attached.

Thanks are due to Dr. D. Chakravarti, D. Sc., Lecturer, Calcutta University for rendering valuable help in the analytical portions in this work. Best thanks of the author are also due to Prof. H. L. Ray, Head of the Chemical Engineering Department and Dr. T. Sen, Principal, College of Engineering and Technology, for rendering all facilities for carrying out this piece of work.

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Received October 11, 1947.